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Improving agricultural carbon monitoring with Sentinel-2 and eddy-covariance-based plant productivity estimates

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ABSTRACT

Carbon balances of croplands are often assessed using models that depend critically on accurate estimates of soil carbon inputs such as crop residues, dead roots, and root exudates. Here, we develop a method to estimate soil carbon inputs by combining satellite-based gross primary productivity (GPP) estimates with harvest yields extracted from agricultural statistics. We model the daily GPP as a statistical regression on photosynthetically active radiation and the red edge chlorophyll index measured by the Sentinel-2 satellites and train the model using data from five eddy covariance flux measurement sites. When tested with leave-one-site-out cross-validation, the model predicted the yearly GPP with a root mean squared error equal to about 10% of the mean. We furthermore show that the predicted cumulative GPP explains 60%–70% of the observed variability within a set of 135 above-ground biomass measurements collected on 40 agricultural fields. Finally, we apply the method to three Finnish regions and estimate the soil carbon inputs as the difference between the net primary productivity (NPP), assumed 50% of the GPP, and the carbon removed in harvest. Compared to the allometric method used in the current national greenhouse gas inventory, our annual carbon inputs are within 5%–30% for wheat but 50%–100% higher for barley, 40%–50% higher for green fallows, and 100%–160% higher for forage grasses. By highlighting a discrepancy between the current national greenhouse gas inventory and carbon budgets derived from eddy covariance measurements, these results provide a path towards closer integration of Earth observation and flux measurement data into greenhouse gas inventories and reporting systems.

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Introduction

Reliable methods to monitor and predict changes in the stocks of soil organic carbon (SOC) are required for understanding the climate impacts of different land management practices [1,2]. Deforestation, agricultural expansion, and conventional farming practices have resulted in a decline of carbon storage in soils [3], and many agricultural soils remain sources of carbon dioxide (CO₂), [e.g. 4,5]. However, when successfully implemented, regenerative agricultural practices provide an opportunity to reverse SOC loss [6,7]. To support policy development, many countries and companies rely on stand-alone soil carbon models [8] to assess the evolution of the soil carbon stocks. The predictions of these models rely on accurate specification of soil carbon inputs such as crop residues and root litter [9,10].

Currently, soil carbon input is often estimated from harvest yields using allometric equations such as [11] that convert yields to biomass. However, different equations can produce inconsistent results, leading to uncertainties in SOC estimates [10,12]. An alternative to the allometric functions might be offered by satellite remote sensing, which by continuously monitoring plant photosynthesis could provide a top-down

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constraint for the soil carbon input. Here, we present a quantitative comparison between a satellite-driven approach and an existing allometric method for estimating soil carbon inputs on a regional level.

Remote sensing approaches for monitoring crop productivity have focused on estimating photosynthesis rates (gross primary production, GPP) and biomass densities. Above-ground biomass density or yield can be estimated directly from remotely sensed canopy reflectance using machine learning trained on biomass measurements [13–16]. A limitation for applying these approaches for soil carbon inputs is that the full turnover of assimilated carbon might not be captured by estimating only the instantaneous above-ground biomass. A more comprehensive approach overcoming this limitation is to assimilate remote sensing-derived biophysical variables, such as LAI, to process-based models. Process-based models have been extensively used in yield estimation [17,18] and for simulating CO₂ fluxes [19,20], but they require detailed soil and management information from the fields and can be computationally demanding which hinders their scalability.

In contrast to machine learning or process-based models, a simple approach to estimate plant photosynthesis is to use remotely sensed vegetation indices either directly as predictors of photosynthesis or via the light-use-efficiency (LUE) model [21]. For example, [22–24] showed that at a monthly time interval, vegetation indices serve directly as a good proxy of photosynthesis across different biomes. However, photosynthesis is not only driven by photosynthetic capacity, but also by solar irradiation and environmental factors, especially at shorter time steps. In the LUE model, the gross primary production is calculated as the product of photosynthetically active radiation (PAR), the fraction of absorbed PAR (fAPAR), and LUE, which represents the efficiency of converting absorbed light into carbon. The fAPAR is typically estimated using vegetation indices, while LUE is estimated based on biome types and environmental factors such as temperature and vapor pressure deficit. Calibrating the vegetation indices for fAPAR and determining the biome-specific LUE is a challenge [25]. The problem can be simplified by taking advantage of the close link between fAPAR, LUE and the canopy chlorophyll content [26] and modeling the GPP as a function of PAR and a vegetation index sensitive to the chlorophyll content. In this approach, also used in the present study, the vegetation index is assumed to capture the joint effect of both fAPAR and LUE [27].

Satellite remote sensing-derived GPP has been used to estimate yield by accumulating the GPP over the growing season using MODIS [28] and Landsat data [29]. High resolution Sentinel-2 data enables estimation of GPP at finer spatial scale [30], such as individual field parcels [31–33]. However, it is currently unclear how the soil carbon inputs predicted by these methods compare with traditional allometry-based estimates.

In this study, we aim to estimate soil carbon input starting from parcel-scale plant productivity derived from data measured by the Multispectral Instrument (MSI) onboard the Sentinel-2 (S2) satellites. Building on the earlier work [27,30,34], we began by developing a nonlinear regression model to describe daily photosynthesis, using the red edge chlorophyll index $CI_{rededge}$ and photosynthetically active radiation as explanatory variables, and calibrated it with carbon flux estimates from eddy covariance (EC) stations. We interpolated the $CI_{rededge}$ values for days with missing satellite data to be able to predict GPP over seasonal and yearly scales, and validated the estimates through comparisons with eddy covariance and biomass data. Finally, we combined the satellite-derived plant productivity estimates with crop yield statistics to estimate soil carbon input across three regions in Finland, and compared the estimates to those derived from yields as used in the national greenhouse gas inventory.

Our approach determines the soil carbon input as the difference of net carbon assimilation and harvest yield, which makes the estimate less sensitive to variations in carbon allocation than typical allometric methods. This may improve the accuracy particularly for the below-ground carbon inputs (e.g. root turnover), which are generally found to be only weakly constrained by the harvest yields [12,35,36]. By improving the robustness of soil carbon input estimates, our approach can contribute to better carbon models and inform agricultural policies to enhance carbon sequestration.

Materials and methods

The overall design of the present study is outlined in Figure 1. The main steps include preprocessing the EC flux measurements from five sites in Finland, fitting the regression model, and evaluating the model results using leave-one-site-out cross-validation and by comparison against biomass measurements from 40 additional sampling sites. Locations of the EC and biomass sampling sites are shown in Figure 2. Finally, we apply the method on regional level by evaluating the net primary productivity (NPP) for crop parcels

Figure 1. Schematic diagram describing the data flow and computation steps. Abbreviations: GPP and NPP, gross and net primary productivity; CAMS, Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service; S2, Sentinel-2.

Figure 2. Map of the study area. The large red markers denote the eddy covariance measurement sites (Flux measurements), the small blue markers denote the biomass sampling sites (Biomass measurements). Shaded areas denote the South Ostrobothnia (SO), Southwest Finland (SF) and North Savo (NS) regions (Regional GPP and soil carbon inputs) for which the regional-scale GPP, NPP and soil carbon inputs were estimated.

randomly selected from the national land parcel identification system. The regional NPP estimates are further combined with survey-based yield statistics to estimate regional-scale soil carbon inputs.

Our approach emphasizes consistent propagation of uncertainties. We use Bayesian techniques for fitting the regression model and for temporal interpolation of the satellite data, and quantify the predictive uncertainties by sampling the posterior probability distributions. The uncertainty estimates account for uncertainties stemming from the model training data and from data gaps in the satellite time series. A Bayesian mixed effects model is used to estimate the joint effect of prediction and sampling errors on the regional GPP and carbon input estimates.

Flux measurements

Eddy covariance measurements and data processing

Net CO₂ fluxes were measured with the EC technique at five different cropland sites in Finland listed in Table 1. Four of the sites are located in southern Finland in Uusimaa (SMEAR-Agri Haltiala and SMEAR-Agri Viikki), Southwest Finland (Qvidja) and Kanta-Häme (Hauho) regions, and one site is located further north in the North Ostrobothnia region (NorPeat, Ruukki). Ruukki has peat soil, Haltiala, Viikki and Qvidja are on fine textured clay soils while the Hauho site is on a more coarse textured silty loam. The measurement periods varied across the sites from 1.5 to 5.5 years between May 2018 and December 2023. During the measured years, forage grasses (timothy, meadow fescue and clovers) were grown in Qvidja, while oats were grown in Hauho. The remaining three sites were under mixed rotations consisting of both forages and cereals. Some of the datasets are previously published (Qvidja: [37], Ruukki: [38]). These datasets were recalculated to make the data post-processing harmonious between all the sites in this study. The recalculated fluxes did not change significantly from the previously published datasets.

The EC instrumentation was similar in all the sites. CO₂ mixing ratios were measured with an enclosed-path CO₂/H₂O gas analyzer (LI-7200, LI-COR Biosciences, USA), and the three-dimensional wind was recorded with a sonic anemometer (u-Sonic3 Scientific, METEK GmbH, Germany). The sampling rate was 10 Hz. Measurement height varied from 2.3 m in Qvidja to 3.3 m in Ruukki. The sample air was transported to the gas analyzer via a 60–91 cm long heated tubing with a flow rate of 12 L min⁻¹. Auxiliary meteorological measurements of air temperature and relative humidity (Humicap HMP155 or HMP110, Vaisala Oyj, Finland), soil temperature (Pt100 IKES sensors, Nokeval Oy, Nokia, Finland or Teros-12, METER Group, USA), soil moisture (ML3 ThetaProbe sensor, Delta-T Devices Ltd., Cambridge, UK or Teros-12, METER Group, USA) and photosynthetically active radiation (PQS 1 PAR sensor, Kipp & Zonen B.V., Delft, the Netherlands or LI-190R quantum sensor, LI-COR Environmental GmbH, Germany) were measured close to the EC tower. The data were collected with a Vaisala QML logger (Vaisala Oyj, Finland) and stored as 30-min averages.

The half-hourly turbulent CO₂ fluxes were calculated with the Eddypro software (v. 7.0.9, LI-COR Biosciences, USA) following standard quality control and corrections protocols. First, the 10 Hz raw data was screened by de-spiking, amplitude resolution and absolute limits after which 1% of the 30-min raw data was allowed to be missing or the 30-min period was discarded. Next, double rotation of the coordinate system was applied to align the sonic anemometer along the local wind streamlines [39], and the data were block-averaged over each 30-min period to remove the linear trends [40]. Time lags between the gas analyzer and sonic anemometer signals were determined by automatic time lag optimization. The effect of water vapor and temperature fluctuations on flux measurements with the LI-7200 was accounted for internally within the analyzer and with a long enough sampling line. The spectral losses caused by block averaging and attenuation of the highest frequencies in the co-spectra of the vertical wind speed and CO₂ mixing ratio were corrected by applying the method by [41]. The 30-min fluxes were screened for relative stationarity and integral turbulence characteristics

Table 1. Measurement period, crop, soil texture (USDA), geographic coordinates and number of days available for model fitting from each site.

Site	Measurement period	Crop	Soil texture	Geographic coordinates	Days available for model fitting
Qvidja	8 May 2018–19 December 2023	Grass	Clay loam	60°17.723'N, 22°23.509'E	71
Ruukki	1 January 2020–20 December 2023	Grass/Cereal	Peat	64°41.036'N, 25°06.382'E	92
Viikki	1 January 2020–19 December 2023	Grass/Cereal	Clay loam	60°13.188'N, 25°01.237'E	21
Haltiala	29 May 2021–20 December 2023	Grass/Cereal	Silty clay	60°16.301'N, 24°56.669'E	77
Hauho	29 June 2022–31 December 2023	Cereal	Silty loam	61°08.388'N, 24°35.067'E	32

[42]. The flux was discarded if the combined flag of these tests indicated the lowest quality on a three-level flagging system [43]. Also, the periods of weak turbulence were removed by applying a friction velocity (u^*) threshold. This threshold was estimated with the moving-point-transition method [44]. Finally, a source area analysis was carried out to filter out flux data that did not represent the target area. This was performed by calculating the cross-wind-integrated footprint distribution from the EC tower to the edge of the field by applying a micrometeorological footprint model developed by [45]. The data were discarded if the cumulative footprint was smaller than 70%. At our sites, the 70% cumulative EC footprint was typically reached at distances within 50–200 m. The data coverage for each site can be found in Table S3.

Gap-filling and partitioning

The data were gap-filled using deep ensembles of neural networks [46]. We used a five-model ensemble and each base model was a sequential model with two hidden layers with 50 nodes and nonlinear ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) activations. Each model was used to predict the mean and the logarithm of the scale parameter of a Laplace distribution to account for heteroscedastic noise in the EC data. The Laplace negative log likelihood was used as the loss function. The weights were randomly initialized using HeNormal initialization [47]. We used the Adam optimizer for training [48] and 10% of data were used as a validation set for early stopping with a patience of 20 fitting rounds. As predictors we used PAR, air temperature, soil temperature and soil moisture at 5 or 10 cm depth, vapor pressure deficit, number of days from the previous harvest and two cyclical functions describing time of day and season [49]. Implementation was done using the TensorFlow library [50].

When estimating uncertainty in the CO_2 fluxes, or net ecosystem exchange (NEE), we took into account uncertainty related to measurements, gap-filling and u^* filtering. Measurement uncertainty was estimated from model residuals using the linear relationship between flux magnitude and the standard deviation of residuals [51]. Gap-filling uncertainty was estimated by combining aleatoric and epistemic uncertainty of model predictions. These were calculated using the predicted mean and scale of the Laplace distribution and the variance of model predictions. The uncertainty related to the u^* threshold was propagated into NEE by filtering the data with varying thresholds, gap-filling the alternative data and calculating the variance of NEE.

The gap-filled data were partitioned into total ecosystem respiration (TER) and GPP. TER was assumed to follow the Arrhenius-type model described by [52]:

$$\text{TER} = R_0 \times e^{E \left(\frac{1}{T_0} - \frac{1}{T - T_1} \right)} \quad (1)$$

where R_0 ($\text{mg CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) is the ecosystem respiration at 283.15 K, E (K) is the temperature sensitivity of respiration, $T_0 = 56.02$ K, $T_1 = 227.13$ K and T is the measured air temperature. The temperature sensitivity of respiration was determined from nighttime ($\text{PAR} < 20 \text{ mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) data using a 15-day moving window with minimum 20 observations per fit and at least a 5 K temperature range. E was determined as the median of successful fits (<50% standard error). R_0 was fitted using 7-day moving windows while keeping E fixed. After deriving both parameter estimates, TER was modeled using air temperature and subtracted from NEE to obtain GPP. The uncertainty in NEE was propagated to GPP by partitioning the NEE data with varying u^* thresholds and individual model predictions of the gap-filling ensemble. Only daily GPP values with a maximum of 70% gap-filled data were used for fitting the S2-based GPP model.

Model input data

Vegetation index

The developed GPP model is based on the $\text{Cl}_{\text{rededge}}$ vegetation index which is sensitive to chlorophyll content [53,54]. The index has performed well in previous studies estimating GPP with LUE-based models [27,30,34], and it produced the best-fitting model among six vegetation indices tested when fitting our S2-based GPP model (Supplementary Figure S2).

The $\text{Cl}_{\text{rededge}}$ was derived from the Copernicus Sentinel-2 satellite data. Sentinel-2 consists of two satellites Sentinel-2A and Sentinel-2B which together result in two to three day revisit time in Finland. We used the bottom-of-atmosphere reflectance products (level-2A) available from the Google Earth Engine

(GEE). The scene classification data included in the level-2A products was used to determine image acquisition dates when the field was not contaminated by cloud or cloud shadow or covered by snow or water. The reflectance data for each field parcel was retrieved with 10 m spatial resolution. For the regional-level analysis, we retrieved the field parcel boundaries from the Geospatial aid application (GSAA) data provided by the Finnish Food Authority [55]. Otherwise, we used known field parcel boundaries. For the EC sites, the satellite imagery was extracted for a target area that coincided with the typical EC footprint. The CI_{rededge} vegetation index was calculated for all pixels within the field parcel using Sentinel-2 reflectance bands B5 (705 nm) and B7 (783 nm) as in [53] and [34]:

$$CI_{\text{rededge}} = R_{\text{NIR}}/R_{\text{rededge}} - 1, \quad (2)$$

where R_{NIR} and R_{rededge} are Sentinel-2 bands B7 and B5, respectively. The mean CI_{rededge} of all pixels within the field parcel was used to represent the CI_{rededge} of the field.

Solar radiation

To estimate the gross primary productivity, the vegetation index is combined with the daily flux of PAR. The radiative flux is obtained from the gridded data product of the Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service (CAMS) All-Sky Radiation (<https://atmosphere.copernicus.eu/supplementary-products>), which consists of radiative fluxes derived from a combination of satellite products [56,57] in a 0.1 degree geographical grid over Africa and Europe. To evaluate the daily PAR, we extracted the 15-min time series of global irradiation for the centroid of each field parcel, aggregated to daily time resolution and multiplied the values with a PAR fraction of 0.5.

Modeling the primary productivity

We assumed that the mean response of GPP, μ_{GPP} , is a function of the vegetation index CI_{rededge} and photosynthetically active radiation, given by

$$\mu_{\text{GPP}} = \frac{a \times CI_{\text{rededge}} \times \text{PAR}}{b + CI_{\text{rededge}} \times \text{PAR}}, \quad (3)$$

where a is defined as the product of a global component a_{glob} and a site effect a_i , and b is a global parameter. This hierarchical structure allows us to capture the global pattern in GPP while accounting for site-specific differences. Due to data limitations, crop-specific effects were not incorporated into the model even though different crops were grown across the study sites, and at three of the sites, the crop type varied between years. The possible impact of crop type on GPP is discussed in the Results section.

To account for uncertainties, the standard deviation of GPP, σ , was defined as

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\sigma_{\text{EC}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{model}}^2}, \quad (4)$$

where σ_{EC} represents the uncertainty in EC-derived GPP, and σ_{model} represents residual errors accounting for daily variability not resolved by the regression model.

The observed GPP values, denoted as GPP_{obs} , were assumed to follow a normal distribution with mean μ_{GPP} and standard deviation σ , such that

$$\text{GPP}_{\text{obs}} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_{\text{GPP}}, \sigma). \quad (5)$$

Using Bayesian inference, the observed variability between sites is also incorporated into the model, allowing the propagation of this variability into the uncertainty estimates for predictions. The posterior distributions for both global and site-specific parameters were estimated using Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling. We used the No U-Turn Sampler [58] as implemented in the numpyro package [59,60]. The priors used for the model parameters are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary of prior distributions used in the hierarchical Bayesian model for gross primary production. Normal distribution with given location and scale parameters but restricted to positive values is denoted by $\mathcal{N}^+(\cdot)$.

Parameter	Description	Prior distribution
a_{glob}	Global effect for a	$a_{\text{glob}} \sim \mathcal{N}^+(0, 60)$
a_i	Scaling effect for a specific to site i	$a_i \sim \mathcal{N}^+(1, \omega)$
ω	Scale of site-specific effects	$\omega \sim \mathcal{N}^+(0, 0.5)$
b_{glob}	Global effect for b	$b_{\text{glob}} \sim \mathcal{N}^+(0, 120)$
σ_{model}	Residual uncertainty	$\sigma_{\text{model}} \sim \mathcal{N}^+(0, 6)$

Temporal interpolation of CI_{rededge}

Despite the relatively frequent overpasses of Sentinel-2A and 2B, data gaps are common during the growing season due to cloud contamination, and the vegetation index therefore needs to be interpolated in time to evaluate the daily GPP. We interpolated the vegetation index using a Gaussian process (GP) regression [61–63], which is a non-parametric Bayesian technique where the values for unobserved times are sampled from a multivariate normal distribution conditioned on the observed values. A key advantage of the Gaussian process technique is its built-in uncertainty quantification. The predictive uncertainties are automatically calibrated to the input data, and the local prediction error grows as the time gap between two observations increases.

The interpolation given by a GP is controlled by a mean function and a covariance kernel. The mean function prescribes the deterministic component in the data, and is here set to zero at all times. The interpolation thus tends towards zero (together with increasing variance) as the time to the closest observation increases. This is acceptable for interpolating the vegetation index under northern conditions, since extended periods with no data are typically associated with either snow or bare soil conditions.

The covariance kernel parametrizes the stochastic component of the GP. Since the vegetation index generally varies smoothly in time, we used a squared exponential kernel with a diagonal term, which is commonly used to model smooth signals contaminated by noise [61]. The kernel depends on three hyperparameters describing the amplitude of the temporally correlated component, amplitude of the uncorrelated component (noise), and the correlation time scale. The hyperparameters were estimated separately for each site and year. We implemented the Gaussian process regression using the `tinygp` package (<https://tinygp.readthedocs.io>), and used the `numpyro` package [59,60] for hyperparameter inference. Technical details regarding the implementation are given in S1.1.

To reduce uncertainty in the interpolation process during winter, we set the vegetation index to zero when fields were covered by snow. This was done based on the scene classification layer provided with the S2 data. However, since the classification occasionally indicated snow-covered conditions during summer, a quality control step was implemented to determine the plausibility of snow cover. First, the vegetation index was interpolated excluding snow-covered times, and 100 realizations of the GP were sampled. Then, for each observation where snow cover was indicated, an independent two-sided t-test was performed against the null hypothesis of vegetation index equal to zero. Snow classifications with p -values below 0.01 were rejected as improbable. Finally, the vegetation index was interpolated with zero values inserted for the plausible snow classifications.

The assumption of a smoothly varying vegetation index is violated when grasslands are harvested. To accommodate this, we implemented a modified squared exponential kernel describing a piece-wise smooth function with a finite number of discontinuities. With this modification, the interpolated values are only informed by observations within the same interval delineated by the harvests. The harvest dates were generally available for the experimental sites but were unavailable for the randomly sampled field parcels (Regional GPP and soil carbon inputs), and for these sites, the presence of discontinuities was estimated as a part of the inference process as described in Sect. S1.1.3.

Cross-validation

To evaluate the ability of the model to generalize across different sites, we conducted leave-one-site-out cross-validation. Here, data from one site was excluded and used as a validation set, while the model was

fitted using data from the remaining sites. This process was repeated five times, such that data from each site was used as the validation set once.

During each iteration, site-specific scaling effects (a_i) for the excluded site were not available, and predictions were made by sampling site-specific effects from the posterior predictive distribution using the posterior distribution of the scale parameter, denoted by ω in Table 2. Thus, for the left-out-site, the total uncertainty in predictions included contribution from the variability of the site-specific scaling effects a_i in addition to the variability of the global parameters (a_{glob} and b_{glob}) and the residual uncertainty (σ_{model}).

Model performance was evaluated using the root mean squared error (RMSE), mean bias (MB) and the coefficient of determination (R^2) calculated using EC-derived GPP values and the predicted values for the excluded site. Additionally, we evaluated the calibration of predictive uncertainties by comparing the observed and predicted probabilities. This was done by calculating the proportion of observed data points that fell within specified predictive intervals. Here, we added the uncertainties in EC-derived GPP to the predictive uncertainties to take into account also the observational errors [64].

Biomass measurements

To complement the leave-one-site-out cross-validation using the flux measurements, we tested the relationships between the predicted cumulative GPP and measured above-ground biomasses from 40 sampling sites (Figure 2). While our method does not directly estimate plant biomass, the growth of above-ground biomass cannot exceed the gross carbon assimilation, and we therefore expect a monotonic relation between crop biomass and the cumulative GPP.

The biomass measurements were extracted from the Carbon Action dataset [65–68], which contains data from 20 Finnish farms participating in a carbon farming experiment. The dataset includes c.a. 2 ha field plots of annual crops and ley, on both conventionally and organically managed farms. For each site, the data include a control plot and a treatment plot testing a carbon farming practice as described in [69]; in this study, no distinction was made between these two plots. The biomass was measured by cutting 4–6 biomass quadrats (33-by-33-cm) from each plot, around three GPS located sampling points. Since the fields were regularly tilled and reseeded, the spatial variability in biomass was low and the quadrat size was considered adequate for capturing representative estimates for the plots. The biomass was cut to 1 cm from the soil surface. The wet biomass was measured on site in July, and a sample of the biomass was taken to oven drying to determine dry matter content.

For each biomass measurement, we evaluated the sum of daily GPP for the corresponding plot either from the beginning of the year (for annual crops and grasslands before harvest) or from the previous harvest or mowing (for grasslands after a harvest). Grazed plots were omitted due to the uncertainties in quantifying the biomass change due to grazing livestock. We also omitted measurements that consisted of stubble or mowed plant biomass left on the field. Total of 135 measurements out of the original 182 were kept following these criteria.

Regional GPP and soil carbon inputs

Using the satellite-based GPP method, we estimated the mean annual GPP during 2020–2023 for croplands managed for wheat, barley, forage grasses and green fallows over three administrative regions (counties) in Finland, shown in Figure 2. The estimated GPP was further converted to the NPP and combined with regionally reported harvest yields to estimate the annual soil carbon inputs, i.e. the part of NPP that is not exported in harvest. The four crops were chosen to cover a range of contrasting management practices, and to include economically important crops for each of the regions. The three regions (Southwest Finland, South Ostrobothnia and North Savo) differ in climatic conditions and include a primarily cereal-growing region (Southwest Finland), a grasslands-dominated region (North Savo), and a region with mixed land use (South Ostrobothnia).

The regional GPP was estimated by survey sampling. For each year, region and crop we evaluated the GPP for $n = 100$ agricultural parcels sampled from the land parcel identification system maintained by the Finnish Food Authority. The parcels were sampled with a probability proportional to size (surface area) without replacement. As discussed below, this strategy reduces the uncertainty when estimating the

area-weighted mean within the population, which is the quantity required for evaluating aggregate carbon fluxes over the regions. The parcels were resampled for each year, and a total of 4800 site-years were therefore processed to evaluate the regional GPPs.

The uncertainty of regional GPP estimates is a function of the sampling error and the random and systematic errors in the GPP model. The model uncertainty was estimated by Monte Carlo sampling. For each site, we sampled 100 realizations of the Gaussian process to determine the uncertainty of the vegetation index fed to the GPP model, and simultaneously, we sampled the posterior parameter distribution of the regression model ([Modeling the primary productivity](#)) to include the effect of parametric uncertainty. Site-specific model parameters were resampled for each site, while the site-independent model parameters were sampled only once and applied uniformly over all sites and years for a given crop and region.

The regional mean GPP in the full population was then estimated by fitting a Bayesian mixed effects model to the sample and following the survey methodology outlined in [70]. This approach proceeds in two steps: first, we estimate a set of parameters which define the distribution of GPP within the population. Then, we sample GPP over the entire population of parcels using the parameter estimates from the first step. The uncertainty of population parameters estimated in the first step is propagated to the second step. An initial examination of the sampled GPP showed weak but significant correlations between the parcel size and GPP (Fig. S4), and our model therefore includes a correction term for the parcel size effect.

The mixed effects model assumes that the yearly GPP for each sampled parcel can be decomposed to additive terms as

$$y_i = x_i + \beta(s_i - \bar{s}) + \varepsilon + \delta_i, \quad (6)$$

where y_i is the observed GPP for the i th sampled parcel, x_i is the parcel's GPP in absence of the parcel size effect, and δ_i and ε are the site-specific and site-independent errors. The observed value y_i is taken equal to the mean of the posterior predictive distribution of the regression model ([Modeling the primary productivity](#)). The term $\beta(s_i - \bar{s})$ allows for a linear association between the parcel size s_i (given as the deviation from the average parcel area \bar{s} in the sample) and the parcel GPP. We assume that the unadjusted GPP x_i is normally distributed with a mean μ and variance σ^2 that are estimated along with the slope β .

The model is solved using the MCMC method (similarly to [Modeling the primary productivity](#)) assuming the prior distributions listed in Sect. S1.2. This results in a posteriori samples for μ , σ^2 and β , which in turn are used for sampling the posterior predictive distribution of GPP for the unobserved parcels. The values within each MCMC sample are then aggregated in space to evaluate the posterior distribution of the area-weighted mean over the full population of parcels. This value differs from the mean of x_i if the parcel size effect parameterized by β is significant. However, as the parcels were sampled with probability proportional to size, the difference is minimized since the deviations from the sample mean parcel size \bar{s} are, on average, smaller for the parcels with the largest contribution to the weighted mean.

Soil carbon inputs

The soil carbon inputs in croplands consist mainly of harvest residues, stubble, litter, and dead roots and root exudates [11], and possibly exogenous inputs such as imported manure or compost. The exogenous C inputs are not considered in this study, and since field crops lack long-lived pools of woody biomass, the carbon inputs on annual level are nearly equal to the difference of the net primary production (GPP minus autotrophic respiration) and the carbon removed in harvested biomass.

We used our regional GPP estimates to estimate soil C inputs on a regional scale by scaling the GPP into NPP and subtracting the harvest yields reported in the statistical database of the Natural Resources Institute Finland (<https://www.luke.fi/en/statistics>),

$$F_C = r_{\text{NPP}} \times \text{GPP} - f_C Y_{\text{DM}}. \quad (7)$$

Here, F_C denotes the carbon input, f_C is the mass proportion of carbon in plant biomass, Y_{DM} is the crop yield as dry matter, and r_{NPP} is the ratio of net to gross primary production. Harvest residues in Finland are generally either left on the field or used for animal bedding, and following [71], we considered only the grain and forage harvests to be exported from the ecosystem.

The crop yield statistics are based on a survey conducted yearly and are given on the same regional level as our GPP; this level of aggregation is also used in the CO₂ emission calculations in the Finnish national emission inventory [72]. The reported crop yields were converted to dry matter assuming a 14% moisture content for cereals and hay and a 66% moisture content for silage. The carbon content f_c of 0.45 g C g DM⁻¹ was used for all crops [71].

Estimates of the NPP:GPP ratio in different ecosystems generally range between 0.2 and 0.8 but are centered at approximately 0.5 [73–76], which is here adopted as the central estimate for r_{NPP} . We modeled the uncertainty of the ratio r_{NPP} as a normally distributed random variable with standard deviation of 0.1 consistent with [73], sampled r_{NPP} as a site-independent random effect, and proceeded with the mixed-effects model following the steps described for GPP in the previous section.

We compared our C input estimates with those evaluated using the method currently used in the national greenhouse gas inventory for Finland [71,72], which applies a combination of allometric coefficients and prescribed root and shoot biomasses to evaluate the yearly C inputs based on the reported crop yields. Similar to the approach of [11], the method partitions the soil C inputs to above-ground residues, root biomass and rhizodeposition. The above-ground residues are calculated from the yield using a harvest index, except for green fallows, for which prescribed biomass inputs are used. The root biomass is calculated using shoot:root ratios for cereals and other annual crops, and for grass crops, prescribed root biomass is used. The rhizodeposition is calculated proportional to the root biomass using a fixed root turnover rate. We calculated these allometry-based C inputs using the coefficients listed in [71] for the same regions and years as our Sentinel-2 based estimates.

Results

Model fit and leave-one-out cross-validation

The relationship between EC-derived GPP and $Cl_{\text{rededge}} \times \text{PAR}$, along with the fitted model and its predictive uncertainty, is shown in Figure 3. GPP across all sites increased with increasing $Cl_{\text{rededge}} \times \text{PAR}$ but the rate started to plateau for higher $Cl_{\text{rededge}} \times \text{PAR}$ values. At higher levels of radiation and increased vegetation cover, the GPP estimates from different sites were more variable. GPP for forage grasses and cereals appeared somewhat distinct, but the difference could also be attributed to the site effect (Supplementary Figure S5), as the EC-derived GPP estimates for Qvidja were consistently lower than the S2-based estimate derived using a model fitted to data from all sites. However, the majority of the daily GPP sums fell within the predictive uncertainty range.

Results from the leave-one-site-out cross-validation showed that the mean RMSE of the GPP model was 1 g C m⁻² d⁻¹ on the daily scale and 31 g C m⁻² mo⁻¹ on the monthly scale (Figure 4), with little variation between sites (1.2–1.7 g C m⁻² d⁻¹ and 28–34 g C m⁻² mo⁻¹). The EC-derived GPP ranged from no uptake during

Figure 3. Relationship between EC-derived daily GPP and the product of the vegetation index Cl_{rededge} and photo-synthetically active radiation (PAR). The markers represent GPP values for five sites and the error bars indicate 95% confidence intervals. The solid line is the predicted GPP (without site-specific effects) and the gray shaded area is the 95% posterior predictive interval.

Figure 4. Comparison between Sentinel-2 (S2)- and EC-based GPP sums at (a) daily, (b) monthly and (c) annual timescales across five sites. The results are from leave-one-site-out cross-validation. In (b) and (c) the error bars represent 95% confidence intervals (EC) and 95% predictive intervals (S2). The dashed line is the 1:1 line. The metrics shown include the root mean squared error (RMSE), mean bias (MB) and the coefficient of determination (R^2). In (a) and (b) the statistical indicators are means for the five sites and in (c) they were calculated using all available years.

Figure 5. Example time series of Sentinel-2 (S2) based and EC-based GPP for a cereal crop year at Hauho (a) and forage grass year at Ruukki (b). The S2-based GPP was estimated using a model that was trained without EC data from the site. The shaded areas for EC-derived GPP are the 95% confidence intervals and for S2-based GPP they are the 95% posterior predictive intervals.

winter to a maximum of $23 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ and $510 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ mo}^{-1}$. The coefficients of determination were 0.91 and 0.95 for daily and monthly sums, respectively. The annual GPP sum ranged from $670 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ to $1460 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ and the model RMSE was $122 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$, corresponding to about 10% of the mean annual GPP over the sites. The mean bias for annual sums was $29 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ and R^2 was 0.70.

Evaluation of the predictive uncertainties showed that for daily sums they were too wide, particularly when considering all seasons (Supplementary Figure S3). However, when focusing on months with potential CO_2 uptake (May–October) the predicted probabilities aligned more closely with the observed probabilities, suggesting that especially the uncertainties for wintertime GPP were excessively wide. Similarly, for monthly sums, the predictive uncertainties were slightly too wide when all seasons were included. For the growing season months, the predicted probabilities matched observed probabilities very well, indicating good calibration of the predictive uncertainties for these months. The uncertainty estimates for annual sums could not be evaluated due to the low number of annual totals.

To illustrate the results of leave-one-site-out cross-validation, S2-based estimates of GPP are shown together with EC-derived GPP in Figure 5 for site-years with an annual crop and forage grass cultivated. The S2-based method successfully captured the significant decline in GPP following harvests and the subsequent regrowth of forage grass also in the fall (Figure 5b). However, in some instances, the S2-based method underestimated the highest GPP values (Figures 5 and 4b). Nevertheless, the error margins of both methods largely overlapped.

Figure 6. Relationships between measured above-ground biomass densities and the remote sensing-derived cumulative gross primary productivity. For annual crops (panel a), the GPP is accumulated from the beginning of the year. For forages (panel b), the GPP is accumulated either from the beginning of the year or from the previous harvest.

Figure 7. Spatiotemporal variability of GPP for each crop within each region. Each distribution corresponds to one-year GPPs over the total 400 sampled land parcels for the years 2020–2023.

Estimates of above-ground biomass

We evaluated relationships between the above-ground biomass densities sampled on 40 sites and the cumulative GPP estimated using the model fitted with data from all EC sites ([Biomass measurements](#)) while distinguishing between annual crops and perennial forages, and between organic and conventionally cultivated fields ([Figure 6](#)). For both annual crops and perennial forages, the above-ground biomass was positively correlated with the cumulative GPP (R^2 between 0.63–0.68, $p < 0.01$).

The ratio between above-ground biomass and cumulative GPP can be interpreted as a lower bound for the NPP:GPP ratio required for calculating soil carbon inputs. On average, the above-ground biomass amounted to $37\% \pm 3\%$ of the cumulative GPP (ratio of average biomass and average cumulative GPP; bootstrap mean and standard error). The ratio did not differ significantly between forages and annual crops ($p = 0.85$; permutation test) but was higher ($p < 0.001$; permutation test) for conventional ($41\% \pm 4\%$) than organic management ($31\% \pm 4\%$).

Regional scale primary productivity and carbon inputs

The patterns of primary productivity over the sampled land parcels ([Figure 7](#)) were similar across the three regions of the study. On average, the parcels cultivated for forages had higher yearly GPP (1200–1300 g C m^{-2})

Figure 8. Regional carbon fluxes for 2020–2023 estimated using the allometric method (AM) and the Sentinel-2 (S2) based method. The sum of all flux components is equal to the net primary productivity (NPP). The harvest C flux is based on a statistical survey for both methods. The AM-based C fluxes are broken into above and below-ground components as described in [Soil carbon inputs](#).

than parcels growing wheat or barley ($850\text{--}1000\text{ g C m}^{-2}$). The GPP of wheat fields was about $50\text{--}100\text{ g C m}^{-2}$ higher than that of barley, and the GPP of green fallows ($1100\text{--}1200\text{ g C m}^{-2}$) was between the cereals and forage grasses. The estimated GPPs are in line with those in the training data, where the annual GPPs were on average 950 g C m^{-2} for cereals and 1300 g C m^{-2} for grasslands.

The regional GPP estimates were converted to NPP, fed into a Bayesian mixed effects model for uncertainty estimation, and compared to the values derived from agricultural statistics using a set of allometric coefficients ([Regional GPP and soil carbon inputs](#)). As shown in [Figure 8](#), the satellite-derived NPP estimates were higher than the allometry-based estimates for all crops and regions. Since the soil C inputs are in both methods equal to the difference of NPP and the harvest yield, the estimated soil C inputs were also higher in the satellite-based approach. The differences were most pronounced for forages, for which the satellite-based approach yielded up to 70% higher NPP estimates and up to 160% higher soil C inputs. The differences were also substantial for green fallows, and for cereals in regions with low harvest yields.

Despite the differences in absolute levels, the satellite-based and yield-derived NPP estimates for cereals showed a positive linear correlation ($R^2 = 0.70$, $p < 0.001$) over the three regions and four years ([Figure 9a](#)). However, the yield-derived NPPs showed a higher variability, spanning a range of $150\text{--}200\text{ g C m}^{-2}$ for each crop, whereas the satellite-derived NPPs were within $100\text{--}150\text{ g C m}^{-2}$ of each other. Both methods predicted a higher NPP for wheat than barley fields, however, the contrast was weaker in the S2 method. The linear relation between S2 and yield-based NPPs had a positive intercept, and thus, the difference between the methods was largest when the NPP was lowest. In contrast to the cereals, the yield-derived NPP for grasslands ([Figure 9b](#)) was not significantly correlated with the GPP-derived estimates. For green fallows, the allometric method uses fixed values for root and shoot biomass, and does not show interannual variations or differences between the regions in this study.

On regional level, the predictive uncertainties (standard deviation) of our estimates were between 7% and 8% of the mean for GPP and 20%–25% of the mean for NPP (Table S4). The largest source of uncertainty were the global (site-independent) parameters in the GPP model ([Modeling the primary productivity](#)); the higher relative uncertainty of NPP is caused by the uncertainty of the NPP:GPP ratio. The remaining uncertainties, caused by the sampling error, aggregated site-dependent uncertainty and the parcel size correction, were small: if the mixed-effects model is fit without the systematic errors (not shown), the uncertainties in regional estimates would be reduced to a few percent of the mean.

Figure 9. Relationship between the yearly NPP estimated using reported yields and allometric coefficients and the NPP estimated from the satellite-derived GPP for a) barley and wheat and b) forages over all regions and years. Each marker denotes the regional average of the given year.

Discussion

Reliability of plant productivity and biomass estimates

Our results demonstrate the overall reliability of estimating plant productivity using Sentinel-2 chlorophyll index ($CI_{rededge}$) and photosynthetically active radiation. Since the model fit showed no clear dependence on crop species, we used the same model parametrization to model both cereals and grass crops. Site-dependent effects could not be ruled out, and our model is structured to include their impact in the predictive uncertainties. However, even when accounting for site-to-site variability, the root mean square error in the leave-one-site-out cross-validation remained at around 10% of the measured yearly mean (Figure 4). Therefore, we conclude that our method provides robust estimates of gross primary productivity (GPP) across diverse conditions, which is crucial as the first step towards biomass estimates.

However, the critical step in estimating biomass inputs involves subtracting autotrophic respiration from GPP to obtain net primary productivity (NPP) and, ultimately, biomass production. While few studies have quantified the NPP:GPP ratio in boreal croplands, our 40%–60% range can be weighed against the biomass measurements as discussed in [Estimates of above-ground biomass](#). Combining the shoot:root ratios and root turnover rates given in [71] with the 41% ratio (conventional cropping systems) of above-ground biomass to cumulative GPP results in a NPP:GPP ratio of 51%. An identical calculation using data from organic systems yields a lower NPP:GPP ratio of 39%; however, the allometric coefficients in [71] might not represent the higher below-ground allocation observed in crops grown in organic systems [77]. Together with the strong correlation between cumulative GPP and measured biomass densities (Figure 6), these values support our range of NPP:GPP ratios.

Comparability to yield-based productivity estimates

Our NPP and soil carbon input estimates were higher than those used in the national greenhouse gas (GHG) inventory for barley, forages, and green fallows (Figure 8). For wheat, the estimates in the national inventory are slightly lower, but well within the uncertainty of our satellite-based estimates, especially for years and regions with high harvest yields. However, the satellite-based method does not reproduce the large contrast in NPP between barley and wheat. In the allometric method, the contrast stems mainly from the different harvest indices used for barley and wheat, whereas in our satellite-based estimates, the difference between the two crops is approximately proportional to the difference in harvest yields.

The most significant discrepancy between the predicted carbon inputs occurs for green fallows and grass crops. Two considerations support the validity of our higher plant productivity estimates for grass crops compared to the national GHG inventory. First, the satellite-based GPP estimates are consistent with those derived from eddy covariance data, and achieving similar NPP estimates as the national GHG inventory would require assuming NPP:GPP ratios between 30% and 35%. Values this low are neither

consistent with the ratios derived from the biomass measurements in this study nor with earlier estimates for managed grasslands or croplands [76,78], which tend to be above 50%. Second, in Sweden and Finland, soils with a history of forage cultivation have been found to have higher biomass and soil carbon stocks than croplands used for cereal production [79,80]. This pattern is not captured by the allometric method, which predicts lower C inputs for grass crops. Although lower tillage intensity in forage cultivation may explain some of the difference [81], the difference may also reflect the importance of below-ground carbon inputs in grasslands [82–84]; these carbon inputs are difficult to estimate from field measurements but can be informed by measurements of the plant CO₂ exchange.

A contrast between cereals and grass crops also emerges when comparing the interannual and regional variations predicted by the satellite- and yield-based methods. For cereals, our method and the national inventory captured qualitatively similar variations in NPP (Figure 9a). However, our method predicted a smaller variability between years and regions by predicting higher NPPs for the years and regions with low yields. Our method thus appeared to provide a more stable estimate of productivity for cereals than the harvest yield, which may be more sensitive to crop management and drought or nutrient stress. For grass crops, the predictions were uncorrelated. This may be caused by the higher diversity of forage crops grown on grasslands, but may also reflect the limitations of using average forage yields as a proxy for estimating productivity. Specifically, the yields might not capture variability of below-ground biomass, but also, some variations of the reported yields may stem from management decisions, such as the number of harvests per year, which are affected by local demand for livestock feed and are not directly coupled to the annual NPP.

Limitations

While our comparisons indicate the potential advantages of our method, it is essential to consider the limitations and challenges associated with its application. First, the accuracy of our biomass production estimates is limited by the uncertainty in the NPP:GPP ratio, which itself is likely to depend on climate and management conditions [76,85,86]. Improved mechanistic understanding of plant C allocation [87], as well as in-situ measurements specific to boreal croplands, may help to better constrain the ratio in the future. Additionally, while our method enables high-resolution estimation of plant productivity, accurate final estimates of soil carbon inputs rely on the reported yield data. This underscores the importance of reliable harvest information. Finally, our method is limited by the ability of the $Cl_{rededge}$ vegetation index to capture variations in the canopy photosynthetic potential. More advanced methods [e.g. 32,88] that use additional environmental drivers (e.g. surface temperature) might be more responsive to weather-induced variations, such as drought impacts.

Future improvements to our method should aim at reducing systematic errors and further improving their quantification. The predictive uncertainties of our regional estimates were up to 7%–8% for GPP and 25% for NPP. These error estimates are plausible given the cross-validation results (Model fit and leave-one-out cross-validation), since some cancellation of errors is expected when the estimates are aggregated over a large number of parcels. These estimates are, however, sensitive to the partitioning of the model uncertainties between the site-dependent and site-independent components. Using training data from a larger and more diverse set of flux measurement sites could improve the bottom-up error estimates, improve robustness of the cross-validation, and allow a more conclusive evaluation of site or crop-dependent effects in the model parameters.

The effects of our plant productivity and soil carbon input estimates on the total carbon balance should be tested using soil carbon models and validated against cropping experiments or soil carbon inventories. In the Finnish context, the allometry-based method was found to underestimate the present-day carbon stocks when tested against a national-scale soil carbon data set [71]. The higher productivity estimates derived from satellite data would help correct this bias.

Broader context and implications

Our method, which combines satellite vegetation index data with eddy covariance flux measurements, provides a cost-efficient and transparent way of monitoring agricultural productivity and soil carbon input.

The method can be adopted in different regions, as the satellite and PAR data are available worldwide, and eddy covariance stations and networks can be used for extending the model calibration and validation.

The satellite-based carbon input estimates address a critical knowledge gap in the current practical, large-scale monitoring methods for agricultural carbon balance. Our approach enhances the accuracy of carbon models in greenhouse gas inventories and informs more sustainable agricultural practices, helping to quantify and optimize carbon sequestration. This improved accuracy supports effective climate and agriculture policies by providing reliable data on agricultural carbon dynamics, ultimately helping policy-makers, food companies, and farmers achieve sustainability targets.

Future work should aim to extend this approach beyond Finland to a broader range of climates, soils, and management systems, and prioritize synchronized and standardized sampling of both satellite and ground-based observations to improve model calibration and validation.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization JL, ON, JV; data curation MiK, MaK, TM, ON, MP, HV; formal analysis HV, JV; funding acquisition HA, JL, AL, TM, MP; investigation HA, MiK, MaK, JL, AL, TM, ON, MP, HV, JV; methodology MiK, JL, ON, HV, JV; project administration JL; resources HA, JL, AL, MP; software ON, HV, JV; supervision HA, JL, AL, MP; writing – original draft MiK, JL, ON, HV, JV; writing – review and editing HA, MaK, AL, TM, MP.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Data availability statement

Data for the eddy covariance measurements and code for the model trained on them is available at <https://doi.org/10.57707/fmi-b2share.353cc686b81449d69117df30aeb3613c> (visited 29 June 2025). The biomass sampling data are available in the datasets [63,64,65,66] cited in Biomass measurements. The Sentinel-2 data are available via the Google Earth Engine, <https://earthengine.google.com/> (visited 2024/12/12). The CAMS radiation data are available at <https://ads.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/datasets/cams-gridded-solar-radiation> (visited 12 December 2024). The land parcel identification data are available at the Finnish Food Authority at <https://www.ruokavirasto.fi/en/about-us/published-datasets/spatial-data-sets/> (visited 12 December 2024). The crop yield statistics are available at the Natural Resources Institute Finland <https://statdb.luke.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/en/LUKE/> (visited 12 December 2024). All other data used in this study are available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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